

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

FROM THE PHYSICAL REALITY OF IMAGINARY NUMBERS IT FOLLOWS THAT THE INVISIBLE AFTERLIFE WORLD PREDICTED BY ALL RELIGIONS ACTUALLY PHYSICALLY EXISTS.

Antonov A.

PhD, HonDSc, HonDL, H.ProfSci

Independent researcher, Kiev, Ukraine

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975059>

Abstract

The article proves that the generally accepted version of STR, which states that imaginary numbers are physically unreal, is incorrect. Experimental evidence is given of the general scientific principle of the physical reality of imaginary numbers, with the use of which a corrected version of the SRT was created. She argues that in addition to our visible universe, there are many other mutually invisible universes in nature. And they form the actually physically existing afterlife invisible world, predicted by all religions.

Keywords: imaginary numbers, special theory of relativity, invisible universes, afterlife invisible world

1. Introduction

Imaginary numbers, discovered about 500 years ago by Scipione Del Ferro, Niccolo Fontana Tartaglia, Gerolamo Cardano, Lodovico Ferrari and Raphael Bombelli [1], are known to everyone and are currently used in all exact sciences. They are even studied in school mathematics courses. But unlike other numbers that are understandable to everyone - integers and fractions, positive and negative, scalar and vector, etc. - their physical essence has not yet been explained. Indeed, what 2 kg., 3 m., 4 sec. is clear to everyone, but what is 2i kg., 3i m., 4i sec., where $i = \sqrt{-1}$, no one can explain. Nevertheless, no one cared about this, just as, for example, now no one cares that the phenomenon of ball lightning is not explained.

But at the beginning of the 20th century, Joseph Larmor [2], Nobel Prize winner Hendrik Anton Lorentz [3], Jules Henri Poincaré [4], Nobel Prize winner Albert Einstein [5] and other outstanding scientists created a special theory relativity (SRT), which is rightly considered to be an outstanding scientific achievement of physics of the 20th century, since it proposed the principle of relativism. And which is therefore now studied in all physics textbooks used in the educational process even at the most prestigious universities. However, in this theory, calculations using relativistic formulas, which were the final result of all reasoning, in some cases led to a result measured by imaginary numbers. And this result already needed to be explained.

After all, no one would need a theory that even its creators could not explain. But the authors of SRT did not know how to do this. And the fate of the service station hung in the balance. But it was saved by the fact that an additional postulate was introduced into the SRT, called the principle of not exceeding the speed of light, from which it followed that quantities measured by imaginary numbers do not exist in nature. And therefore, there is no need to explain them.

This is the form in which SRT is still taught.

2. The physical reality of imaginary numbers.

But besides SRT there are other sciences. Including the theory of electrical circuits, which is used in radio engineering, electrical engineering and computer science. Fundamental to this theory is Ohm's law [6], [7], discovered in 1826 for DC electrical circuits, which is now studied even in school physics textbooks. And in 1893, Charles Proteus Steinmetz proposed its interpretation of Ohm's law for alternating current electrical circuits [8], which is now used daily by millions of engineers around the world in their work. In this theory of electrical circuits, the imaginary resistances of capacitors and inductors, which can be measured by instruments, were recognized as actually physically existing. And if these imaginary resistances were recognized as physically unreal, as follows from SRT, then neither radio engineering, nor electrical engineering, nor computers, nor radio measuring instruments should exist.

Fig. 1. In any radio-technical laboratory there are devices called frequency response meters, which prove the physical reality of imaginary and complex numbers by their mere existence

But they do exist. And thereby they prove the physical reality of imaginary numbers [9]-[33]. Consequently, by the existence of radio- and electrical engineering, the generally accepted version of SRT was refuted even before its creation. Other proofs of the physical reality of imaginary numbers have been published in [34]-[46]. Therefore, the logical conclusion is that the version of STR currently presented in all physics textbooks is incorrect [47]-[66].

3. Physical reality of invisible parallel universes

In the existing generally recognized version of STO from its relativistic formulas and the principle of non-exceeding the speed of light also follows that in nature there is only our visible universe in which everything is measured only by real numbers.

However, in the corrected version of STR [67]-[74], from its relativistic formulas it follows that in our Multiverse [75]-[85], in addition to our visible universe, there are also about twenty other mutually invisible parallel universes.

Fig. 2. Scheme of an astronomical experiment to detect invisible universes

And one can be convinced of their existence [86]-[91], as a result of astronomical observations of the starry sky in portals [92]-[94], since the constellations in them will differ - and the further into the portal one penetrates, the greater the differences will be - from the constellations observed at the same time in the same region outside the portals. And since there are a lot of anomalous zones [95]-[98] on Earth, presumably being entrances to portals, some observatories have already are located in such anomalous zones. Like, for example, the main astronomical observatory of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, located in Goloseevsky forest 12 km from the center of Kyiv. Therefore, in order to verify the existence of neighboring invisible universes adjacent to our visible universe, it is enough to compare on a computer the observations of this observatory with the observations of neighboring observatories located outside the anomalous zones.

4. Why, despite all the refutations of the generally accepted version of SRT, set out in all physics textbooks, it continues to be taught.

But this simple and low-cost experiment, which in the most indisputable way will allow us to answer the question of whether there are invisible universes neighboring our visible universe, no one has done or is going to do. Obviously, because physicists do not need such an answer, since it will refute the version of STR studied in textbooks.

The corrected version of STR states that imaginary numbers are physically real and invisible universes exist. Therefore, having become convinced of the existence of invisible universes, we will have to admit that the corrected version of STR is correct and once again be convinced that imaginary numbers actually physically exist. And then it will inevitably be necessary to explain their physical meaning of imaginary numbers.

And it is obvious - in addition to our visible world, there is an invisible world.

5. The existence of a physically real invisible world

However, the usefulness for science of the above experimental evidence of the physical reality of imaginary numbers goes beyond problems of correcting the version of SRT given in physics textbooks. From experimentally proven principle of the physical reality of imaginary numbers, one will inevitably have to conclude that the results of all studies described by imaginary numbers in all other exact sciences also are physically real.

Then many difficult questions will arise. For example, what exists in the looking glass when we see ourselves in the mirror? And therefore, in the end, we will have to admit that in addition to our visible world, there is also a huge (most likely even much larger than our visible world) invisible world [99]-[107].

Indeed, in addition to the room in which we are now and which we see, there are a large number of other invisible to us rooms in other apartments, houses, cities and countries. The same situation is in space - in addition to our visible universe, in other dimensions there are about twenty other parallel universes of the hidden Multiverse that are invisible to us. And outside of our hidden Multiverse in the Hyperverses, there are many other Multiverses.

And the existence of such a world invisible to us, in which Gods and the souls of the dead live, was long predicted by all world religions. Consequently, what these religions say about the world order, about the afterlife, is true. And therefore, all of us, the inhabitants of planet Earth, will now have to believe in this and adjust our behavior accordingly.

6. Conclusion

The author hopes that the information presented in the article will be an incentive to unite the efforts of science and religions in their activities for the benefit of people.

Acknowledgments

The author is cordially grateful for the understanding, comments and help of his wife Olga Ilyinichna Antonova.

References:

- Weisstein E.W. (2005). The CRC Concise Encyclopaedia of Mathematics. 3-rd ed. CRS Press. Boca Raton. FL.
- Ohm G. S. (2014). Die galvanische Kette. Verlag Der Wissenschaften. Ohm Göttingen.
- Ohm G. S. (2015). Gesammelte Abhandlungen. Severus Verlag, Hamburg.
- Steinmetz C. P. (2010). Theory and Calculation of Electric Circuit. Nabu Press. Charlstone.
- Larmor J.J. (1897). A Dynamical Theory of the Electric and Luminiferous Medium. Part III. Relations with Material Media. Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences. 190, 205-300.
- Lorentz H.A. (1899). Simplified Theory of Electrical and Optical Phenomena in Moving Systems. Proceedings of the Netherlands Academy of Arts and Science. Amsterdam. 1, 427-442.
- Poincaré H. (1905). On the Dynamics of the Electron. Comptes Rendus. 140. 1504-1508.
- Einstein A. (1905). Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter Körper. Annals of Physic. 17. 891-921.
- Antonov A. A. (2015). Ohm's law explains astrophysical phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy. Global Journal of Physics. 2(2). 145-149.
http://gpcpublishing.com/index.php?journal=gjp&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=294&path%5B%5D=pdf_14
- Antonov A. A. (2015). Adjustment of the special theory of relativity according to the Ohm's law. American Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering. 3(5). 124-129.
doi: 10.12691/aje-3-5-3
- Antonov A. A. (2016). Ohm's Law is the general law of exact sciences. PONTE. 72(7) 131-142. doi: 10.21506/j.ponte.2016.7/9
- Antonov A. A. (2016). Ohm's Law explains phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy. International Review of Physics. 10(2). 31-35.
<https://www.praiseworthyprize.org/jsm/index.php?journal=irephy&page=article&op=view&path%5B%5D=18615>
- Antonov A. A. (2016). Ohm's law refutes current version of the special theory of relativity. Journal of Modern Physics. 7. 2299-2313.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/jmp.2016.716198>
- Antonov A. A. (2021). The version of STR stated in physics textbooks is in-correct because it denies the existence of radio engineering. 82nd International Scientific Conference of the Eurasian Scientific Association "Scientific result in theory and practice". Moscow. ESA. 11-15. <https://esa-conference.ru/sborniki/?y=2021>
- Antonov A. A. (2022). The version of STR presented in physics textbooks is incorrect, since it follows from it that radio engineering should not exist. European Journal of Applied Sciences. Services for Science and Education. UK. 10(1). 440-445.
DOI://doi.org/10.14738/aivp.101.2022
- Antonov A. A. (2022). The existence of radio engineering refutes the physics textbooks' version of STR. The scientific heritage. (Budapest, Hungary). 83(1). 19-22.
DOI: 10.24412/9215-0365-2022-83-1-19-22
- Antonov A.A. (2022). The fundamental Ohm's law in radio engineering as interpreted by Steinmetz, which proves the physical reality on imaginary capacitive and inductive reactances, refuted the version of the STR presented in physics textbooks even before its creation. German International Journal of Modern Science. 26. 50-53. DOI: 10.24412/2701-8369-2022-26-50-63
- Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR stated in physics textbooks is refuted by the existence of radio engineering. Danish Scientific Journal. 56. 56-59.
<http://www.danish-journal.com>
- Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR presented in physics textbooks is in-correct because it denies the possibility of the existence of Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz and, consequently, the existence of radio engineering. Annali d'Italia. 28(1), 43-47.
<https://www.anditalia.com/>
- Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR stated in physics textbooks is refuted by the existence of radio engineering. Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science. 78(1). 63-67. DOI: 10.24412/3453-9875-2022-78-63-66.
- Antonov A.A. (2022). If the physics textbook version of STR were true, then Ohm's law should not exist in nature, and therefore all radio engineering would not exist. International independent scientific journal. 36. 16-19. <http://www.iis-journal.com>
- Antonov A.A. (2022). If the version of STR in physics textbooks were true, then there would be no radar, no television, no radio navigation, no telecommunication and many other things. Journal of science. Lyon. 28. 76-79. <https://www.joslyon.com/>
- Antonov A.A. (2022). The version of STR set out in physics textbooks is incorrect because it states that Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz does not really exist, and therefore radio engineering does not exist either. Sciences of Europe (Praha, Czech Republic). 87(1). 54-57.
DOI: 10.24412/3162-2364-2022-1-54-57
- Antonov A.A. (2022). Why the physics textbooks teach an incorrect version of the special theory of relativity which denies the existence of radio- and electrical engineering. III international scientific conference "Challenges and problems of modern science". London. Great Britain. 78-86. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.528/zenodo.7486814>
- Antonov A. A. (2023). Why is the incorrect version of the special theory of relativity being studied in physics textbooks, refuted the existence of radio- and electrical engineering even before its creation? The scientific heritage. (Budapest, Hungary). 105. 83-89.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7560145

26. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is an incorrect version of the special theory of relativity that denies the possibility of the existence radio and electrical engineering being studied in physics textbooks of physics? German International Journal of Modern Science. 48. 23-29.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7541137>
27. Antonov A.A. (2023). Who needs the incorrect version of special relativity taught in physics textbooks despite all its experimental refutations? Annali d'Italia. 39, 64-70.
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7568916](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7568916)
28. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is incorrect version of the special theory of relativity that denies the possibility of the existence of radio and electrical engineering being studied in textbooks of physics? Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science. 100. 27-33.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528512>
29. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is incorrect version of the special theory of relativity, refuted by the existence of radio and electrical engineering, is still studied in all university physics textbooks? Danish Scientific Journal. 69. 66-72. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692053>
30. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is incorrect version of the special relativity still being studied in physics textbooks, which denies Ohm's law for alternating current used worldwide by millions of radio- and electrical engineers? International independent scientific journal. 46. 38-44. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525751>.
31. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is the generally accepted version of STR, which denies the possibility of the existence of radio engineering and electrical engineering, tsunamis and bell ringing, the physical phenomenon of resonance and Ohm's physical law for alternating current, music created by the piano and even swing swings on the playground, nevertheless is still considered correct and studied in physics textbooks? Sciences of Europe (Praha, Czech Republic). 112. 44-50. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7708515](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708515)
32. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why is the incorrect version of the special theory of relativity still being studied in physics textbooks, despite all its experimental refutations. European Journal of Applied Sciences. Services for Science and Education. UK. 11(2). 61-71.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14738/aivp.112.14128>
33. Antonov A.A. (2023). Why the incorrect version of the special theory of relativity, which denies the possibility of the existence of radio engineering and electrical engineering, has not yet been refuted. Journal of science. Lyon. 40. 19-25.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7704392>
34. Antonov A. A. (2008). Physical Reality of Resonance on Complex Frequencies. European Journal of Scientific Research. 21(4). 627-641. <http://www.eurojournals.com/ejsr.htm>
35. Antonov A. A. (2008). Physical Reality of Resonance on Complex Frequencies. European Journal of Scientific Research. 21(4). 627-641. <http://www.eurojournals.com/ejsr.htm>
36. Antonov A. A. (2009). Resonance on Real and Complex Frequencies. European Journal of Scientific Research. 28(2). 193-204. <http://www.eurojournals.com/ejsr.htm>
37. Antonov A. A. (2010). New Interpretation of Resonance. International Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences and Technology. 1(2). 1-12.
http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2010-888
38. Antonov A. A. (2010). Oscillation processes as a tool of physics cognition. American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research. 1(2). 342-349. doi:10.5251/ajsir.2010.1.2.342.349
39. Antonov A. A. (2010). Solution of algebraic quadratic equations taking into account transitional processes in oscillation systems. General Mathematics Notes. 1(9). 11-16.
http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2010-887
40. Antonov A. A. (2013). Physical Reality of Complex Numbers. International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering. 3(4). 219-230
http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2013-898
41. Antonov A. A. (2014). Correction of the special theory of relativity: physical reality and nature of imaginary and complex numbers. American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research. 5(2). 40-52. doi:10.5251/ajsir.2014.5.2.40.52
42. Antonov A. A. (2015). Physical reality of complex numbers is proved by research of resonance. General Mathematics Notes. 31(2). 34-53.
http://www.emis.de/journals/GMN/yahoo_site_admin/asets/docs/4_GMN9212V31N2.129701.pdf
43. Antonov A.A. (2015). Principle of physical reality of imaginary and complex numbers in modern cosmology: the nature of dark matter and dark energy. Journal of the Russian physico-chemical society. 87(1). 328-355. (In Russian)
http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2015-1119
44. Antonov A. A. (2016). Physical Reality and Nature of Imaginary, Complex and Hypercomplex Numbers. General Mathematics Notes. 35(2). 40-63.
http://www.geman.in/yahoo_site_admin/asets/docs/4_GMN-10932-V35N2.31895146.pdf
45. Antonov A. A. (2017). The physical reality and essence of imaginary numbers. Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science. 6. 50-63. <http://www.njd-iscience.com>
46. Antonov A. A. (2018). Physical Reality and Essence of Imaginary Numbers in Astrophysics: Dark Matter, Dark Energy, Dark Space. Natural Science. 10(1). 11-30.
doi:10.4236/ns.2018.101002
47. Antonov A.A. (2021). The special theory of relativity stated in physics textbooks is incorrect. 77th International Scientific Conference of the Eurasian Scientific Association "Theoretical and practical issues of modern science". Moscow. ESA. 11-15
48. Antonov A. A. (2021). Version of the special theory of relativity that is studied in all physics textbooks is incorrect. Österreichisches Multiscience Journal (Innsbruck, Austria). 43(1). 17-22. <http://osterr-science.com>
49. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity, which is studied in physics textbooks, is incorrect. German International Journal of Modern Science. 16, 49-53.

- DOI:10.24412/2701-8369-2021-16-49-53
50. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity, which is studied in all physics textbooks, is incorrect. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 51(1). 31-35. <http://www.danish-journal.com>
51. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity taught in all physics text-books is incorrect. *Annali d'Italia*. 22(1). 39-44. <https://www.anditalia.com/>
52. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity presented in physics textbooks is wrong. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 68(1). 3-7. DOI: 10.24412/3453-9875-2021-68-3-7.
53. Antonov A. A. (2021). In all physics textbooks an erroneous version of special theory of relativity is given. *International independent scientific journal*. 31.34-39. <http://www.iis-journal.com>
54. Antonov A. A. (2021). Special theory of relativity taught in physics textbooks is wrong. *Journal of science*. Lyon. 23. 47-52. <https://www.joslyon.com/>
55. Antonov A. A. (2021). All physics textbooks study incorrect special theory of relativity. *Sciences of Europe*. (Praha, Czech Republic) 79(1). 30-35. DOI: 10/24412/3162-2364-2021-79-30-35
56. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental proofs of infidelity of the version of the special theory of relativity studied in physics textbooks and the truth of its alternative version. 80th International Scientific Conference of the Eurasian Scientific Association "Development of science and education in the conditions of global instability". Moscow. ESA. 8-17. <https://esa-conference.ru/sborniki/?y=2021>
57. Antonov A. A. (2021). The fallacy of the STR version studied in physics textbooks proved experimentally. *Österreichisches Multiscience Journal* (Innsbruck, Austria). 45(1). 17-26. <http://osterr-science.com>
58. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental evidences for the fallacy of the STR version in the physics textbooks. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*. Services for Science and Education. UK. 9(6). 349-364. DOI:10.14738/aivp.96.11304.
59. Antonov A. A. (2021). If the STR version in physics textbooks were true, we would never have heard the music of the piano and the bell ringing, there would be no television, no cellular telephony, no radar or GPS navigation, we would not even be aware of the existence of resonance and Ohm's law as interpreted by Steinmetz, and our children could not swing on the swings. *The scientific heritage* (Budapest, Hungary). 78(2). 41-50. DOI: 10.24412/9215-0365-2021-78-2-41-50
60. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental refutations of the STR version contained in physics textbooks and confirmations of the truth of its alternative version. *German International Journal of Modern Science*. 22. 52-61. DOI: 10.24412/2701-8369-2021-22-52-61
61. Antonov A. A. (2021). The STR version in physics textbooks must be corrected, because if it were true, there would be no tsunamis or indian summer in nature, we would be never have heard piano music, engineers would be not have been able to create television, cell phones, GPS trackers, and even children would not be able to swing on swings. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 54(1). 29-38. <http://www.danish-journal.com>
62. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental evidence of the incorrectness of the STR version studied in physics textbooks. *Annali d'Italia*. 25(1). 32-41. <https://www.anditalia.com/>
63. Antonov A. A. (2021). The incorrectness of the STR version presented in physics textbooks proven experimentally. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 74(1). 3-7. DOI: 10.24412/2453-9875-2021-74-53-62.
64. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental refutations of the generally accepted version of the SRT studied in physics textbooks. *International independent scientific journal*. 34(1). 23-32. <http://www.iis-journal.com>
65. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental refutations of the SRT version in the physics textbooks. *Journal of science*. Lyon. 26(1). 29-37. <https://www.joslyon.com/>
66. Antonov A. A. (2021). Experimental evidences for the fallacy of the STR version in physics textbooks. *Sciences of Europe* (Praha, Czech Republic). 82(2). 19-28. DOI: 10.24412/3162-2364-2021-82-2-19-28
67. Antonov A.A. (2023). The Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *European Journal of Applied Sciences*. Services for Science and Education. UK. 11(5). 68-83. DOI:10.14738/aivp.115.15474
68. Antonov A. A. (2023). Corrected special theory of relativity. *Journal of science*. Lyon. 47. 14-23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10068983>
69. Antonov A. A. (2023). Corrected special theory of relativity. *Annali d'Italia*. 49, 25-35. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10214679
70. Antonov A. A. (2023). The Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *The scientific heritage*. (Budapest, Hungary). 123. 72-81, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10033028
71. Antonov A. A. (2023). The Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 118. 40-49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10009500>
72. Antonov A. A. (2023). Alternative Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *Sciences of Europe*. (Praha, Czech Republic). 128. 62-71. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10081933
73. Antonov A. A. (2023). Special Theory of Relativity. *German International Journal of Modern Science*. 67. 64-73. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10966458
74. Antonov A. A. (2023). Corrected Version of the Special Theory of Relativity. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 77. 88-97. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054677>
75. Antonov A. A. (2011). Structure of the Multiverse. *British Journal of Science*. 2(2). 51-60. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2011892
76. Antonov A. A. (2012). Multiverse. Time Travels. *International Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences and Technology*. 12(2). 43-56. http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2012-896
77. Antonov A. A. (2012). Discovery of the real multiverse. *encyclopaedia of Russian thought, Reports to the Russian Physical Society*. 16(3). 3-20. (In Russian).

- http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2012-1115
78. Antonov A. A. (2013). Cognition of the multiverse as a factor in accelerating the development of human civilization. *Journal of Russian physical thought*. 1-12, 6-77. (In Russian).
http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2011-1117
79. Antonov A. A. (2015). Hidden Multiverse. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Physical Science*. 2(1). 25-32.
http://doi.org/10.17686/sced_rusnauka_2015-903.
80. Antonov A.A. (2015). The astrophysical phenomenon of dark matter and dark energy proves the existence of the hidden Multiverse. *American Journal of Modern Physics*. 4(4). 180-188. DOI: 10.11648/j.jamp.20150404.14
81. Antonov A. A. (2015). Hidden Multiverse: explanation of dark matter and dark energy phenomena. *International Journal of Physics*. 3(2). 84-87. doi:10.12691/ijp-3-2-6
82. Antonov A. A. (2015). Principles and structure of the real Multiverse: explanation of dark matter and dark energy phenomena. *American Journal of Modern Physics*. 4(1). 1-9.
doi:10.11648/j.ajmp.20150401.11
83. Antonov A. A. (2016). Hypothesis of the Hidden Multiverse: Explains Dark Matter and Dark Energy. *Journal of Modern Physics*. 7(10), 1228-1246. doi: 10.4236/jmp.2016.710111
84. Antonov A. A. (2015). Quaternion structure of the hidden Multiverse: explanation of dark matter and dark energy. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research A: Physics and Space Science*. 15(8). 8-15.
https://globaljournals.org/GJSFR_Volume15/2-Quaternion-Structure-of-the-Hidden.pdf
85. Antonov A. A. (2016). Verifiable Multiverse. *Global Journal of Science Frontier Research: A Physics and Space Science*. 16(4) 4-12 doi: 10.17406/GJSFR
86. Antonov A. A. (2020). How to See Invisible Universes. *Journal of Modern Physics*. 11(05), 593-607. DOI: 10.4236/jmp.2020.115039
87. Antonov A. A. (2020). Can invisible universes be seen? *International independent scientific journal*. 21(2). 51-60. <http://www.iis-journal.com>
88. Antonov A. A. (2020), How to discover invisible universes. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 42(1). 36-48. <http://www.njd-iscience.com>
89. Antonov A. A. (2020). Universes Being Invisible on Earth outside the Portals Are Visible in Portals. *Natural Science*. 12(8). 569-587.
<https://doi.org/10.4236/ns.2020.128044>
90. Antonov A. A. (2020). Invisible universes can be seen in anomalous zones. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 43(1). 9-24. <http://www.danish-journal.com>
91. Antonov A. A. (2021). Invisible universes can be seen in anomalous zones. *International independent scientific journal*. 23(1). 28-44.
92. Antonov A. A. (2012), Earth, portals, parallel universes. *American Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research*. 3(6). 464-473
doi:10.5251/ajsir.2012.3.6.464.473
93. Antonov A. A. (13 January 2016). How Portals of the Invisible Multiverse Operate. *Science PG Frontiers*.
<http://www.sciencepublishing-group.com/news/sciencepgfrontiersinfo?articleid=7>
94. Antonov, A. A. (2016). Star gates of the hidden multiverse. *Philosophy and cosmology*. 6. 11-27. (In Russian). <http://ispcjournal.org/journals/2016-16/Antonov16.pdf>
95. Chernobrov, V. (2000). *Encyclopaedia of mysterious places of the Earth*. Veche Publishing House. Moscow. (In Russian).
96. Chernobrov, V. (2004). *Encyclopaedia of mysterious places of Russia*. Veche Publishing House. Moscow. (In Russian).
97. Chernobrov, V. (2007). *Encyclopaedia of mysterious places of the Earth and space*. Veche Publishing House. Moscow. (In Russian).
98. Chernobrov, V. (2009). *Encyclopaedia of mysterious places of Moscow and Moscow region*. Helios ARV Publishing House. Moscow. (In Russian).
99. Antonov A. A. (2023). Proving physical reality and explaining the physical essence of imaginary numbers. *Norwegian Journal of development of the International Science*. 123. 26-36.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451085>
100. Antonov A. A. (2024). Physical reality of imaginary numbers and their physical essence. *Danish Scientific Journal*. 80. 25-35
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10594282>
101. Antonov A. A. (2024). Proof of physical reality of imaginary numbers and explanation of their physical essence. *German International Journal of Modern Science*. 72. 17-27.
102. Anonov A. A. (2024). Physical reality of imaginary numbers and their physical essence. *Sciences of Europe*. (Praha, Czech Republic). 133(1). 79-90.
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10575590
103. Antonov A. A. (2024). Physical reality of imaginary numbers and their physical essence. *The scientific heritage*. (Budapest, Hungary). 129. 43-53. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10558263
104. Antonov A. A. (2024). Proving Physical Reality and Explaining Physical Essence of Imaginary Numbers. *Journal of science*. Lyon. 50. 25-35.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10609816>
105. Antonov A. A. (2024). Physical reality of complex numbers and their physical essence. *International independent scientific journal*. 58. 3-13.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10491923>
106. Antonov A. A. (2024). Proof of physical reality of imaginary numbers and explanation of their physical essence. *Annali d'Italia*. 51, 25-35. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10573831
107. Antonov A. A. (2021). Physical reality of imaginary numbers and its their physical essence. *The scientific heritage*. (Budapest, Hungary). 129. 41-54.
DOI: 19.24412/9215-0365-2021-73-2-39-43